

AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH TO TEACHING CHEMISTRY AT A MEDICAL COLLEGE

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Annotation: This article mentions one of the pedagogical technologies - an integrative approach. As you know, at present, using pedagogical integrative approaches in teaching pharmaceutical and chemical sciences, one can significantly improve the quality of education.

Key words: chemistry, medicine, method, integrative approach, knowledge efficiency.

Interdisciplinary connections in the study of disciplines such as chemistry, physics, biology and geography in secondary and higher educational institutions are a clear expression of the integration processes taking place in science today. The study of individual issues of a particular academic discipline, based on the knowledge gained in the study of other disciplines, helps students to study the overall picture of phenomena, to cover their multilateral connections, to avoid repetition in the study of various issues, concepts, processes, etc. Among the tasks of teaching the disciplines of the natural science cycle, a special place is occupied by the scientific understanding of the processes occurring in the environment and the formation of a holistic knowledge about nature and man. In addition, it has become possible to apply various models for the implementation of sustainable development ideas both in integrated learning courses and in teaching individual subjects, such as chemistry.

The connection of chemistry with other objects of study is facilitated by the fact that chemistry lessons study material of great importance for other natural sciences that use chemical theories, laws and methods to study natural phenomena. For example, chemical cyclic processes can serve as models of natural processes of development, such as the change of seasons, the change of phases of the moon,

heartbeat, circadian rhythm in plants, changes in animal populations in ecosystems, the formation of minerals in rocks and living organisms.

The use of chemical experiments in integrative classes in the implementation of chemical - medical, chemical - pharmaceutical and intersectoral projects allows college students to develop unified approaches to the formation of a unified natural science picture of the world, strengthening the integration of natural science knowledge and the formation of basic concepts studied in various courses. At the same time, the practical orientation of the content of training courses is enhanced based on the study of phenomena, processes, objects, substances surrounding in everyday life. For example, when conducting experiments on qualitative reactions of cations of the I-analytical group, training was organized in the following order.

Pedagogical tasks:	Learning outcomes:
1. Explanation of qualitative reactions of cations of the I-analytical group;	1. Qualitative reactions of cations of the I-analytical group are shown in the
2. Training in the correct use of equipment required for analysis;	experiment;
3. Explanation of the correct choice and use of group and private reagents;	2. They can properly use the necessary equipment for analysis;
4. To show the correctness of drip and semi-microscopic	3. Understand the correct choice and use of group and private reagents;
and	4. Drip, semi-microscopic and

Interactive methods are used to increase student engagement after conducting experiments.

The "Chamomile Flower" method

To apply the "Chamomile" method, the teacher puts questions behind the petals of the chamomile flower, the students choose the question themselves. When students make omissions and mistakes in answering questions, other students are allowed to correct omissions and mistakes.

Questions about the chamomile method:

1. Which of them belong to the cations of the I - analytical group?

2. What do you know about the solubility in water of hydroxides and salts of cations of the I-analytical group?
3. What properties of ammonium are used to remove the NH_4^+ ion in solution?
4. What compounds of sodium and potassium are used in medicine?
5. What reagents can be used to open Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ ions?
6. Why you should to add sodium acetate to a solution to detect K^+ ions with tartaric acid?
7. In which color do Na^+ , K^+ ions color the flame of a gas burner?
8. Describe the procedure for detecting NH_4^+ ions with an alkali solution?

Indicators and evaluation criteria

Indicators	Evaluations			
	5	4	3	2
Develop knowledge on the topic:	The student provides detailed information on the topic.	The student inaccurately presents information on the topic.	The student presents information on the topic with	Student does not describe the information on the topic at all.
Mastering practical skills: Analysis of "problematic issues"	The student gives a correct, clear, concise answer to the posed situational question.	The student makes some omissions and mistakes when answering the situational	The student either makes big omissions and mistakes, or cannot answer the	The student cannot answer the question.
Formation of practical knowledge and skills	The student demonstrates practical knowledge and skills completely, accurately and correctly.	The student demonstrates unmistakable practical knowledge and skills, but makes mistakes and	The student makes mistakes and omissions both in practical knowledge and in the interpretations of skills	The student cannot show and comment on practical knowledge and skills
Total:	5	4	3	2

During the training, students' knowledge is evaluated and motivation is given to them.

It is planned to develop scientific and methodological recommendations on the criteria of motivation, independent thinking, creativity, modeling of career guidance training of students of medical professional colleges in chemistry and their application in educational activities.

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